

ESRC

Data management plan required?	Yes
RDM policy Link	https://esrc.ukri.org/files/about-us/policies-and-standards/esrc-research-data-policy/
Definition of data	Not specified
Length of data management plan	Not specified
DMP template/ requirements	<p>Which existing data will be used and any requirement for new data. Volume and type of data should also be specified, along with the appropriate standards documentation and metadata.</p> <p>Legal, ethical or commercial restrictions on data sharing - adequate justification for not sharing data must be given. How raw data supporting publications will be accessed. How non-digital data will be stored and accessed.</p> <p>Digitally stored data should be accompanied by a persistent DOI.</p>
Required data repository	Yes. UK Data Service or suitable repository within 3 months of the grant ending. The UK data service will ensure long term access to data according to FAIR principles. Data will be accompanied by persistent object identifiers and citation standard. UK data service will also provide guidance and training on implementing good data management/ sharing.
Time for data release	Embargo period of data can be given for no longer than 12 months from the end of the grant.
Time for long-term storage of data	Not specified
Costings	Applicants must include the costs of data management/ preparation in their grant application. As ESRC funds UK Data Service for long term curation, funds for this cannot be requested in grant.
Last updated	March 2015
Contact Details	escenquiries@esrc.ukri.org
Comments	N/A

Documents used:

ESRC research data policy <https://esrc.ukri.org/files/about-us/policies-and-standards/esrc-research-data-policy/>

ESRC research funding guide <https://esrc.ukri.org/files/funding/guidance-for-applicants/research-funding-guide/>

ESRC research data policy FAQs <https://esrc.ukri.org/files/about-us/policies-and-standards/research-data-policy-faqs/>

UK data service <http://ukdataservice.ac.uk/deposit-data.aspx>

Accessed: May 2018